

UGNIUS 2D Soccer Simulation Team Description

Paper 2024

Nazaninzahra Gholami¹, Tania Ghahremani², Mohadeseh Rostami³,
Zahra Rajabnejad⁴, Maedeh Nemati⁵, Tanaz Shomali⁶

¹ Fatemehzahra High school, Iran

² Sama2 High school, Iran

³ Fatemehzahra High school, Iran

⁴ Motahare High school, Iran

⁵ Mashkat High school, Iran

⁶ Roshddokhtaran High school, Iran

{ nazi1388gh0223, tania.ghahremani88, mo1593mmm, zahra87r99,
maedehnemati86, mrs.tanaz.shomali}@gmail.com

Abstract, Soccer Simulation 2D League is one of the major leagues of RoboCup competitions. In a Soccer Simulation 2D (SS2D) game, two teams of 11 players and one coach compete against each other. Players communicate with the football simulation server. In this paper, we present our idea about improving pass, shoot and dribble in which we tried to consider all possible situations.

Keywords: Pass to teammate, The owner of the ball, The nearest player, Soccer Simulation 2D.

1 Introduction

In this paper, the changes we made on the pass, shoot and dribble sections are described. We tried to code and simulate real soccer techniques. Part two shows how the pass works, and part three explains the logic for the player who wants to shoot, and part four explains the player's dribbling.

1.1 Previous Work

This is the first year that our team participates in RoboCup competitions and is looking for experience. In this year we tried to code the real strategic of playing football simply.

2 Pass

Passing is a key part in the game of football. The aim is to maintain possession to try and create opportunities to score and win the game. Passing allows players to connect with each other and work as a team successfully. If you keep the ball and don't pass, defenders can know where you are and that the ball isn't moving around the field, making it easy for the other team to take possession of the ball.

We implemented the following ideas to improve the construction of the pass section :
In order to solve the problem that when we give the pass to our teammate, the opponent players surround the teammate and take the ball from the player, we used the strategic coordinates of the players in such a way that they give the pass to someone who either none of the opponent players are close to him or to They should give the one who has fewer players in front of him, or to make the game more accurate, we should give the pass to a player who is closer to the opponent's goal so that he can score, or we should give a pass to someone who is parallel to the player who is close to the opponent's goal.

Teammate number 5 is surrounded by more opponents and there is another teammate to the left of the owner the ball who is surrounded by fewer opponents and that player is parallel to the opponent's goal, so he gives him a pass.

3 Shoot

Shooting is one of the applications of Soccer2D to shoot at the opponent's goal by being in the right position, which may turn into a goal.

The players receive the codes with the help of the server, measure the situation and implement the written behaviors through the considered strategies. In the normal game mode and without errors, players are lurking near the opponent's goal and behind the teammates. They shoot them to the closest point of the goal, where the goalkeeper is less likely to catch the ball.

The steps are as follows:

The teammate who owns the ball shoots the ball to the coordinates that are not the opponent's goalkeeper.

If another teammate was near the player who owned the ball and had the conditions to shoot, the player who owned the ball passes to that player and then shoots towards the goal.

4 Dribble

Dribbling is moving along with the ball while bouncing from one place of the court to another. Skilled dribbling can pull opponents to them and create space for the mates or can dribble and reach to the area to score.

The logic of the `bhv_basic_offensive_kick.h` code for the dribble behavior is as follows: 1. Get the player (distance), opponent position (opponentPos) and target position (targetPos) as input to the `dribble_withBall` function. 2. Calculate the distance between the position of the player and the opponent by calculating the absolute value of their difference and storing it in the `distance` variable. 3. Checking if the distance between the player and the opponent (`distance`) was less than or equal to 1:

- The player rotates 180 degrees and calculates his new position using the modulo 360 operator
 - The player should turn his back to the opponent and move towards the goal. If the target position (targetPos) is greater than the player's current position (`distance`), the player's position is increased by one unit, otherwise it is decreased by one unit.
4. Finally, the `dribble_withBall` function returns true to indicate that the dribble was successful.

5 References

1. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2205.10953>
2. <https://www.118file.com/mag/pass-training-and-types-of-passes-in-football/>
3. <https://www.123helpme.com/essay/Football-Passing-46CD42387B7736BC>
4. <https://www.ipl.org/essay/How-To-Pass-A-Soccer-Ball-Essay-BDB13FE4B7C421A7>
5. <https://www.123helpme.com/essay/Essay-On-Dribbling-479178>
6. <https://iranrostov.com/article/art101>
7. <https://medium.com/@LeviSnafu/fancy-footwork-the-art-of-dribbling-in-football-soccer-49ca103c6843>
8. <https://coachingamericansoccer.com/introductions-to-soccer-skills/introduction-to-dribbling/>
9. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332288767_Dribbling_in_football_Confronting_learning_theories
10. <https://honorfardi.com/public-skills/others/dribbles-for-football/>
11. The book "Inverting the Pyramid: The History of Football Tactics" by Jonathan Wilson.
12. FourFourTwo website
13. The book "The Mixer: The Story of Premier League Tactics, from Route One to False Nines" by Michael Cox

14. The book "Zonal Marking: The Making of Modern European Football" by Michael Cox.

15. The book "Soccer Modern Tactics: Italy's Top Coaches Analyze Game Formations Through 180 Situations" by Alessandro Zauli.